

same order of magnitude. β_2 was also higher for Mansbal lake (M_2) sample. It is interesting to note that stability constants followed inversely the degree of humification ($\Delta \log K$ value), as M_2 showed low humification (exhibiting high $\Delta \log K$ value). This is in agreement with Matsuda and Ito⁸, who observed an increase in the stability constants of complexes of humic acids with metal ions such as copper, zinc and lead. It was further observed in our experiment that the stability constants of zinc-humic acid (M_2) complexes were almost equal to that of copper-humic acid complexes ($\beta_1 = 2.0 \times 10^7$ and $\beta_2 = 4.3 \times 10^{10}$), although the two metal ions differ significantly in their reactivity.

TABLE 2—STABILITY OF COPPER-HUMIC ACID COMPLEXES

Site	β_1	β_2
M_2	2.1×10^7	4.5×10^{10}
A_2	19.1×10^8	4.91×10^7
W_2	16.6×10^8	7.06×10^7
D_2	15.8×10^8	1.4×10^9

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Prof. J. Shanker, Prof. M. Y. Qadri and Dr. B. A. Subla of C.O.R.D., Kashmir University.

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Use of Molybdate. Oxidative Decarboxylation of α -Hydroxycarboxylic Acids

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Manuscript received 5 February 1986, revised 25 September 1987,
accepted 30 October 1987

UNLIKE Cr^{VI} compounds, the application of Mo and W as oxidising agents in their higher valency states is very rare in synthetic organic chemistry

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though they belong to the same group of transition elements. It was observed that ammonium molybdate in boiling hydrochloric acid (6N) could convert arylmethanols into the corresponding aromatic aldehydes in good yield¹. This unique oxidation never went beyond the aldehyde stage. In the course of our investigation to explore the scope of this reagent, it was observed that under specific condition this reagent can effect oxidative decarboxylation of certain α -hydroxycarboxylic acids (1) to the respective carbonyl compounds (2).

The oxidations of alcohols using Mo^{VI} complexes², allylic alcohols by molybdenum catalysed *t*-butylhydroperoxide³ and various types of organic compounds employing hydrogen peroxide with molybdate as catalyst⁴⁻⁶ have been reported, and the present investigation describes another new application of Mo^{VI} as an oxidant. Ammonium (or sodium) molybdate is a stable, non-toxic and readily available reagent which may be chosen only with those cases where there is no undesirable side-reaction for boiling the substrate in 6N hydrochloric acid.

Benzilic acid (1; X=Y=C₆H₅) was selected as the pilot compound to establish the optimum condition for the oxidation to yield the desired benzophenone (2; X=Y=C₆H₅). Thus a mixture of benzilic acid (0.5 g) and ammonium molybdate (2.5 g) were refluxed in 6N hydrochloric acid (15 ml) and dimethyl sulphoxide (5 ml) for 4 h. On usual work-up benzophenone was obtained in almost quantitative yield. Replacement of dimethyl sulphoxide by either glacial acetic acid or dimethyl formamide did not affect the yield of the product but the work-up of the reaction mixture was very difficult due to the formation of emulsion. The effect of variation of the refluxing time, reaction temperature and quantity of ammonium molybdate used has also been studied. The variation of the amount of ammonium molybdate revealed that the use of equimolar quantities of the reagent and the substrates was essential for a good yield of the product. It was observed that 2.3 g (0.01 mol) of benzilic acid required 12 g (0.01 mol) of ammonium molybdate and heating under reflux for 4 h with 6N hydrochloric acid was the ideal condition for this oxidation. Similarly, 9-carboxy-9-hydroxy-fluorene was oxidised to furnish fluorenone in quantitative yield. Mandelic acid required almost double the quantity of the oxidant and gave a mixture of benzaldehyde (10%), benzoyl formic acid (60%) and benzoic acid (20%). Other aliphatic α -hydroxy acids like citric, tartaric and glycollic under similar optimum condition furnished the desired oxidation products in only 10–15% yield. It appears that the yield of the desired product would be excellent with aromatic substrates but quite low with aliphatic compounds because of the

undesirable side-reactions. It had been further observed that this oxidation failed in the alkaline medium.

Experimental

M.ps. and b.ps. are uncorrected. Each experiment was repeated several times. Ir spectra were taken in Perkin-Elmer 177 and 297 spectrophotometers.

Oxidation of benzoic acid: A mixture of benzoic acid (0.01 mol, 2.3 g), ammonium molybdate (0.01 mol, 12 g), HCl (6 N; 75 ml) and dimethyl sulphoxide (25 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 h. The deep blue reaction mixture was cooled, poured into water (30 ml) and extracted with a mixture of ether and benzene (1:1, v/v; 3×50 ml). The work-up was difficult due to the formation of an emulsion. The organic layer was washed successively with water (20 ml), caustic soda solution (1 N; 20 ml; preserved), again water (3×20 ml), and then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvent a colourless residue (1.8 g) was obtained which furnished a 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 227–28°, m.m.p. with the authentic 2,4-DNP derivative of benzophenone remained undepressed. The crude ketone was purified by evaporative distillation at 120–25°/12 mm to furnish colourless crystals (1.6 g), m.p. 46°, which remained undepressed on admixture with benzophenone. The ir spectra of the product and authentic benzophenone were identical in all respect; ν_{\max} (nujol) 1980, 1925, 1800, 1645, 1445, 1375, 1315, 1275, 1175, 1150, 1070, 995, 935, 915, 810, 760, 695 and 630 cm^{-1} .

The preserved alkaline extract was acidified (congo red) with concentrated HCl and the precipitated organic acid on usual work-up, drying and removal of the solvent yielded (trace) colourless crystals, m.p. 148°, which remained undepressed on admixture with the starting material.

Oxidation of 9-carboxy-9-hydroxyfluorene: A mixture of 9-carboxy-9-hydroxyfluorene (0.5 g), ammonium molybdate (2.5 g) and dilute HCl (6 N; 25 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 h. The initial deep blue colour gradually turned to light green and finally to brown. The cooled reaction mixture on work-up in the aforementioned method furnished a neutral product (0.4 g) which was purified by evaporative distillation at 120°/12 mm, when pure fluorenone was obtained (0.35 g) as pale yellow needles, m.p. 81°, m.m.p. with the authentic sample remained undepressed. The product furnished a 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 280–83°. The ir spectra of the product and the authentic fluorenone were identical in all respect; ν_{\max} (nujol) 1950, 1925, 1830, 1715, 1610, 1595, 1445, 1370, 1295, 1185, 1145, 1095–1080, 950, 915, 880, 810, 780, 730, 665 and 645 cm^{-1} .

Oxidation of mandelic acid: A mixture of mandelic acid (0.5 g), ammonium molybdate (4 g)

and dilute HCl (6 N; 40 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 h. The blue reaction mixture on similar work-up gave a residue (trace) which furnished the 2,4-DNP derivative of benzaldehyde, m.p. 233–35°. It corresponded to 10% formation of benzaldehyde in this reaction.

The alkaline extract was acidified (cong red) with concentrated HCl and extracted with ether (3×25 ml). The organic layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue (0.4 g), obtained after removal of the solvent, was crystallised from water to furnish benzoic acid (0.1 g), m.p. 120–21°, m.m.p. with authentic benzoic acid remained undepressed. The aqueous mother liquor was saturated with common salt and extracted with a mixture of ether and benzene (3×30 ml). The organic layer was washed with a little water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was removed. The residue, thus obtained, furnished on evaporative distillation at 120–30°/2–3 mm colourless crystals of benzoylformic acid (0.3 g), m.p. 64° (lit^o. 66°), which yielded orange-yellow 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 180–90°. Two more crystallisations of this crude 2,4-DNP derivative from dilute ethanol furnished analytical sample, m.p. 195–96°d (lit^o. 196–97°d) (Found: C, 50.70; H, 3.08; N, 16.95. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$ calcd. for: C, 50.92; H, 3.05; N, 16.96%).

Oxidation of citric acid: A mixture of citric acid (4 g), ammonium molybdate (8 g) and dilute HCl (6 N; 50 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 h. The deep blue colour of the reaction mixture gradually changed to brown. The reaction mixture was slowly distilled to collect a distillate (40 ml) which contained acetone (10%; identified and estimated through 2,4-DNP derivative and iodoform); other product, if any, could not be isolated.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. Prasad Kumar Bhattacharyya, Head, Chemistry Department, for facilities, and Mrs. Gayatri Roy Mahasay for a generous support. One of the authors (B.H.) thanks U.G.C., New Delhi, for a Research Associateship.

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Use of Vanadate. Oxidative Decarboxylation of α -Hydroxy Acids

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VANADIUM(V) is a strong oxidising agent in perchloric acid and it has been found to be effective in dilute perchloric acid, hydrochloric acid or acetic acid for the oxidative decarboxylation of α -hydroxycarboxylic acids. Considering the easy availability and stability of the reagent as well as the easy workup procedure and short reaction time, this method appears to be an excellent one and it can compete with other oxidants¹⁻⁹. So the present investigation was undertaken by selecting readily available benzoic acid as the pilot compound to establish the optimum condition of the oxidation.

Thus a mixture of benzoic acid (**1**; X=Y=C₆H₅; 1 mol equivalent) and sodium (or ammonium) metavanadate (2 mol equivalents) in perchloric acid (70%) diluted with equal volume of water was heated under reflux for ten minutes. As the reaction proceeded the reaction mixture assumed a deep-blue colour which remained unchanged till the end of the reaction. The reaction mixture on usual workup furnished benzophenone (**2**; X=Y=C₆H₅) in 80% yield which remained unchanged on extending the refluxing time upto 4 h or substituting perchloric acid by either hydrochloric acid (6 or 1 N) or glacial acetic acid. The reaction failed in the neutral or alkaline medium and use of less than two molar equivalents of vanadate resulted in the low yield of the desired carbonyl compound. The yield of benzophenone also remained unaltered by employing dimethylsulphoxide or dimethylformamide as solvent or by stirring the reaction mixture at room temperature (25–30 min), but with 9-carboxy-9-hydroxyfluorene, it was necessary to heat the reaction mixture under reflux temperature for at least

10 min. Mandelic acid on similar oxidation did not furnish benzylformic acid; only 15% of benzaldehyde and a trace of benzoic acid were obtained.

Oxidation of aliphatic α -hydroxycarboxylic acids, like citric, tartaric, glycollic, malic and lactic, by similar treatment with vanadium(V) in dilute perchloric acid medium furnished the desired carbonyl compounds (in 10–15% yield) which were isolated from the reaction mixtures through distillation. They were identified through the formation and purification (chromatography over alumina) of the corresponding 2,4-DNP derivatives and m.m.p. determination of the latter with the respective authentic samples. From these experiments it became evident that with aliphatic substrates the present method was unsuitable.

Experimental

Oxidation of benzoic acid (1; X=Y=C₆H₅): To a mixture of benzoic acid (0.6 g) in perchloric acid (70%; 10 ml) and water (10 ml) was added sodium (or ammonium) metavanadate (0.7 or 0.6 g, respectively) and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 10 min under inert atmosphere. The clear deep-blue reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water (20 ml) and extracted (3 × 50 ml) with a mixture of ether and benzene (1 : 1, v/v). The organic layer was washed successively with water (1 × 20 ml), caustic soda (1 N; 20 ml; preserved) and water (3 × 20 ml), then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvent a colourless oily residue (0.5 g) was obtained which furnished a 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 235°, which remained undepressed on admixture with the 2,4-DNP derivative of benzophenone¹⁰. The crude ketone was purified by evaporative distillation at 165–70°/6 mm to furnish colourless crystals (0.4 g; 80%), m.p. 46°, which remained undepressed on admixture with benzophenone. The ir spectra (Perkin-Elmer 297 infrared grating spectrophotometer) of the product and that of the authentic benzophenone were identical in all respect, ν_{max} (nujol), 1980, 1925, 1800, 1640, 1595, 1575, 1445, 1320, 1275, 1175, 1150, 1075, 1030, 1000, 995, 945, 935, 915, 820, 765, 705, 695 and 640 cm⁻¹. Unreacted benzoic acid could not be recovered from the alkaline extract through usual workup.

Oxidation of 9-carboxy-9-hydroxyfluorene: A mixture of 9-carboxy-9-hydroxyfluorene (0.6 g), ammonium metavanadate (0.6 g), perchloric acid (70%; 10 ml) and water (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 10 min. The light green reaction mixture was cooled. On workup in the aforementioned method it furnished a neutral product (0.4 g) which was purified by evaporative distillation at 160–65°/6–7 mm when pure fluorenone was obtained as pale yellow needles (0.3 g, 60%), m.p. 81°, m.m.p. with authentic fluorenone remained undepressed. However, fluorenone was obtained in quantitative yield by heating the reaction mixture for 2 h. The product furnished a 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 280–83° (lit.¹¹ 283°). The ir spectra of

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